

DOES YOUTH UNEMPLOYMENT REDUCE HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX IN NIGERIA?

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effects of youth unemployment on the human development index in Nigeria. The study employed the error correction and the Granger causality model, sourcing its data from the 2023 United Nations Development Program database and the 2023 World Development Indicators between 1991 and 2022. The results revealed a weak short-run effect of youth unemployment and gross secondary enrollment, while gross domestic product exhibits a significant lagged effect. The short-run convergence is strongly corrected to normal after volatility. However, the null hypothesis that youth unemployment and gross secondary school enrollment Granger-cause the human development index in Nigeria was rejected. The long-run and robustness tests indicate mixed but generally modest effects on the human development index. Youth unemployment has led to a lack of necessary skills and education, low productivity, and low international competitiveness, which, in Nigeria, remains a threat to the human development index. Despite various studies aiming to provide lasting policy recommendations regarding the effects of youth unemployment on economic growth and socio-economic issues, none have addressed its impact on the growth of the human development index in Nigeria. This study is the first to contribute to economic literature through the consideration of the effect of youth unemployment on the human development index within the Nigerian economy. The findings of this study imply the development of the human index, recommending that fiscal policy easing, demand-side subsidy programs, regional employment in the manufacture of necessity goods, and recruitment of the youth in the military base, health, and education sectors provoke a structure in labor law enforcement in the private sector.

Keywords: Youth unemployment, human development index, employment theory.

JEL Codes: J21, J64, O15.

1. INTRODUCTION

Securing full employment is crucial for achieving peace, stability, food security, and human development. As the population grows, unemployment rises despite the benefits of increased employment for economic prosperity and sustainable development (Nkechi *et al.*, 2012). The human development index significantly influences discussions around human, economic, and social development, incorporating life expectancy, education, and gross domestic product (GDP) per capita (El-Ghannam, 2002; Biao, 2011; Radovanovic, 2011; Nchofoung *et al.*, 2022). The development of the human index globally comprises a composite measure of three major dimensions: life expectancy, mean years of schooling, and GDP per capita (Taner *et al.*, 2011). An increase in economic growth and higher youth employment improve the human development index (Soubbotina, 2004; Aceleanu *et al.*, 2015). The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) revealed that Africa's human development index is low, indicating higher youth dependency (Kpolovie *et al.*, 2017). The index categorizes countries into low, medium, and high levels, with the majority of African economies falling into the low category (79%) and a significant portion (83%) having the lowest indices (UNDP 2009; UNDP 2010; Taner *et al.*, 2011). Only 49% of the Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) region struggles with low life expectancy, poor nutrition and health access, and literacy rates, alongside a high absolute poverty rate of 54% (Agyepong *et al.*, 2017; Osakede *et al.*, 2023). Also, educational enrollment shows wide gaps across levels, with 85% for primary, 67% for secondary, and 35% for tertiary education, which affects the human development index. Despite resource imbalances, adult literacy has improved, affecting youth unemployment and school dropout rates.

Reports from the 2024 Sustainable Development Goals indicate that declining human development indices significantly reduce the achievement of Goals 4 and 8, which promote quality education and decent employment. In Africa, 40 out of 53 economies face high unemployment rates due to fertility issues affecting the labor force. The African Development Bank (AfDB, 2024) highlights Nigeria's challenges, where a youthful population of 230 million, with 70% under 30, struggles for access to decent jobs. Despite an expected annual economic growth rate of 2.3%, this growing youth demographic projects that 66 million could remain unemployed by 2030, exacerbating economic pressures and hampering human capital development. Nigeria's labor force participation is robust at 80.4%, with a youth unemployment rate of 7.2% as of Q2 2023, reflecting a growing trend (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). The report also reported that a significant portion of the youth, about 13.8%, are not engaged in education, employment, or training, indicating a lost potential economic asset. To enhance human capital and economic growth, there is a need to create formal job opportunities for youth aged 15 to 64. However, many young people are unskilled and lack education, hindering productivity and competitiveness (Anowor *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, macroeconomic instabilities, primarily inflation and stringent government policies, threaten Nigeria's human development index and resource management (Idris, 2021).

Therefore, this study contributes to economic literature in the following ways. First is through the consideration of the impact of youth unemployment on the human development index, which has not been explored or carried out in the literature within Nigerian economies. Research by Ita and Bassey (2022) and Eze *et al.* (2024) explored the relationship between economic factors and socio-economic development, while Ayinla and Ogunmeru (2018) focused on economic development, neglecting the human development index. The studies most relevant to this research gap are Musa *et al.* (2024) and Mbachu (2022) in Nigeria, alongside Olanipekun (2019) in Africa. However, these Nigerian studies did not address youth unemployment and did not utilize suitable data concerning the human development index.

Furthermore, they measured economic development solely through GDP per capita, highlighting a significant gap, as Hasan and Sasana (2020) pointed out that the human development index does not equate to GDP per capita. This study examines the extent to which youth unemployment reduces the human development index in Nigeria, investigating the impact alongside variables such as gross enrollment and inflation rate. It aims to provide recommendations on balancing the contributions of youth unemployment to the human development index. The study is structured into four sections: literature review, methodology, conclusions, and recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the past years, advancements in the dynamic relationship of macroeconomic variables and youth unemployment have altered the development of economic growth theories, yet their theoretical implications have remained underexplored due to different findings. In ASEAN, Hasan and Sasana (2020) identified negative effects of GDP, foreign direct investment (FDI), and inflation on youth unemployment, while highlighting positive impacts from trade openness and the human development index. Sinha (2023) studied India, revealing short-term negative effects of minimum wage on unemployment but a long-term relationship between economic growth and unemployment. Olanipekun (2019) noted that male unemployment adversely affects Africa's growth, while primary school enrollment contributes positively to GDP per capita, suggesting improvements in female employment. Jumptah *et al.* (2020) reported that economic growth policies in Ghana have successfully reduced youth unemployment, with significant impacts from shared growth and development initiatives. Ajeigbe *et al.* (2021) found that manufacturing value added and domestic credit to the private sector had a positive relationship with youth unemployment, whereas FDI and gross capital formation were negatively correlated.

In Nigeria, various studies unveil the complexity of youth unemployment and economic growth. Olubusoye *et al.* (2023) categorize youth unemployment as a structural issue, while Akinbola (2024) emphasizes its detrimental effects on productivity and economic policies. Onwuka and Udeze (2023) discovered correlations indicating that youth unemployment negatively impacts economic growth, yet Obiekezie (2022) contends there's no link and advocates for improved job creation policies. Anyanwu *et al.* (2021) highlight youth unemployment as a socio-political challenge, suggesting measures like promoting entrepreneurship to alleviate the crisis. Ayinla and Ogunmeru (2018) find minimal impact on GDP and productivity despite rising unemployment. Although Adamu and Bulus (2024) revealed that a reduction in population growth alone does not significantly affect the unemployment rate. Specifically, Ochinyabo (2021) found that population growth, remittances, GDP, and unemployment negatively impact the human development index, while foreign direct investment and effective governance have positive effects. Serifat (2020) identifies root causes such as corruption and lack of skills, and Omoyele *et al.* (2022) argue that poverty drives youth unemployment without a clear causative relationship with economic growth. Adenike (2021) indicates that poverty exacerbates unemployment and security spending, underscoring a cycle of insecurity. Lastly, Omini Eko and Adofu (2022) found that unemployment exacerbates brain drain, infant mortality rate, and out-of-school children.

Furthermore, extant studies summarized the critical and mixed findings on the effect of youth unemployment and economic growth (for instance, Serifat, 2020; Anyanwu *et al.*, 2021; Obiekezie, 2022; Onwuka & Udeze, 2023; Ihugba *et al.*, 2024; Akinbola, 2024), establishing its granger causality (Omoyele *et al.*, 2022); the spillover of youth unemployment among different sectors such as agriculture, industry, services is frictional or not (Olubusoye *et al.*, 2023); governance and youth unemployment (Eseyin *et al.*, 2021; Agbai & Adesanya, 2023),

industrialization and youth unemployment (Atan & Effiong, 2020), entrepreneurship development and youth unemployment (Chukwuma & Imide, 2023), youth unemployment on socio-economic development (Ita & Bassey, 2022; Eze *et al.*, 2024), youth unemployment and economic development (Ayinla & Ogunmeru, 2018), youth unemployment and crime (Ajaegbu, 2012; Adebayo, 2013; Onwuka *et al.*, 2020; Magaji *et al.*, 2022), and the link between government sectoral spending and human development in Nigeria (Onabote *et al.*, 2023). Despite these efforts, studies in the literature have not captured the effect of youth unemployment on the growth of the human development index in Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Theoretical framework

Economic theories examine the relationship between unemployment, wages, and prices, with foundations in classical and Keynesian models. The study adopted the classical theory, or employment theory, which asserts that full employment occurs without inflation under perfect competition, a homogeneous labor force, flexible wages, and no government intervention (Gordon, 1974). It contends that unemployment arises from wage rigidity, with the equilibrium of demand and supply leading to full employment (Hall *et al.*, 1975; Stiglitz, 1984). In this model, stable long-term employment is achieved when all individuals voluntarily work at existing wage rates, despite diminishing production returns. Key factors influencing employment and output include output, labor supply, wage, capital stock, and technical knowledge. The model is expressed in equation (Eq.) 1 as,

$$Y = f(U, K, w, T) \quad \dots \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where Y is the output level, U is the supply of labour force (employment level), w is the wage structure, K is the capital stock, and T is the advancement of technological knowledge. Furthermore, as argued by the model, Labor force participation is crucial for individuals to earn income and enhance their quality of life, impacting economic human development. To improve development indices, youth unemployment must be eliminated since youth are key to the working population. While output rises with workforce expansion, diminishing marginal returns occur past a certain labor threshold. High youth unemployment affects the ability to achieve full employment, thus influencing human development indices.

3.2. Model Specification

In investigating how youth unemployment reduces the human development index in Nigeria, the study augmented the classical employment model as specified in Eq. 2 with the assumption of no technology advancement.

$$Y_t = f(U_t, w_t, K_t) \quad \dots \text{Eq. 2}$$

Replacing Y_t the level of output as a measure for human development index, U_t as youth unemployment since is represents the supply of labour force in which if not addressed for full employment in the case of Nigeria leads to unemployment of the working population, w_t proxy for as inflation rate due to the prevailing wage rate to determine the purchasing power of individuals, K_t as the stock of capital proxy with rate of secondary school gross enrollment. This is expressed in Eq. 3 as,

$$HDI_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 YUN_t + \gamma_2 GES_t + \gamma_3 INF_t + \gamma_4 GDP_t + \rho_t \quad \dots \text{Eq. 3}$$

As expressed in model Eq. 3, HDI_t is the human development index at time t ; YUN_t is youth unemployment; GES_t is the gross enrollment of secondary school at time t ; INF_t signifies the inflation rate at time t ; GDP_t is the gross domestic product at time t ; γ_0 is the constant parameter;

$\gamma_1 - \gamma_4$ are the coefficients of the estimated parameters, and ϱ_t is the corresponding white noise of the estimated model at time t . Expectedly, a unit increase in youth unemployment and inflation is predicted to harm and bring about a decrease in the human development index, while a unit increase in gross enrollment in secondary school and gross domestic product is predicted to have a unit increase in the human development index.

3.3. Data, scope, and source

The human development index is sourced from the 2024 United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), while the percentage of gross enrollment in secondary school, the modeled percentage of the ILO unemployment estimate of the youth labor force between the ages of 15 and 24, the inflation rate (the annual percentage of consumer prices), and the annual percentage of the gross domestic product growth rate were sourced from the 2024 World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI). The justification for the selection of youth unemployment and inflation rate is supported by Anyanwu *et al.* (2021), Obiekezie (2022), and Olubusoye *et al.* (2023). To this end, a decrease in youth unemployment and inflation promotes the equitable distribution of wealth with an enhanced standard of living. In Nigeria, where long-term wage data is often unreliable, inflation serves as a proxy for measuring real wages, reflecting the actual purchasing power of incomes. To justify the selection of inflation rates, it shows that rising inflation diminishes the real value of wages, thereby affecting households' ability to meet basic needs like nutrition, healthcare, and education. These basic needs influence the index of human development when nominal wages do not adjust adequately; higher inflation leads to reduced real wages, making it a key indicator of living standards. In studies on youth unemployment and human development, controlling for inflation reveals the macroeconomic pressures that negatively affect real earnings and worsen welfare for unemployed and low-income individuals. Likewise, to justify the selection of the annual growth rate of the gross domestic product, see Anyanwu *et al.* (2021), Obiekezie (2022), Onwuka & Udeze (2023), and Olubusoye *et al.* (2023). With a high gross domestic product, the expectation of crimes, social unrest, and incidence of poverty and youth unemployment is expected to reduce. These data were all sourced between the period of 1991 and 2022 due to the high rate of youth unemployment since the last military regime and the early sustained era of democracy, as the incidence of democracy strictly affects the present state of young unemployment, then having a sustained long-run effect on the development of the human index in Nigeria. However, due to the lack of Nigeria's youth unemployment data from it, the study is limited in covering recent years.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Pre-estimation techniques utilized included descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and unit root tests. Descriptive statistics focused on analyzing the series with metrics such as mean, standard deviation, kurtosis, and skewness to reveal its historical behavior. A pairwise correlation examined relationships among youth unemployment, the human development index, and relevant control variables. The Phillip-Perron unit root test assessed the stability and responsiveness of the series to shocks, chosen for its corrective capacity regarding non-parametric heteroscedasticity and serial autocorrelation in errors.

4.1.1. Summary of the descriptive statistics and pairwise correlation matrix

Table 1 revealed the summary of the descriptive statistics, indicating that Nigeria's human development index has a mean of 0.48, with low positive volatility and a range from 0.44 to 0.54. This reflects low human capital and employment rates. Youth unemployment is significantly high at a mean of 10.30 percent, presenting a leptokurtic distribution and a volatile performance around its mean, which can hinder economic development. The negative

perception of education among the youth, fueled by macroeconomic factors such as an inflation rate of 18.4 and a gross domestic product of 4.05%, exacerbates the issue. Both inflation and gross domestic product exhibit leptokurtic behavior and positive skewness, indicating ongoing economic pressures that limit growth and employment opportunities for the youth.

Table 1 also displays the pairwise correlation matrix, revealing significant relationships in Nigeria’s economic indicators. Youth unemployment and gross secondary enrollment positively correlate with the human development index at 0.85 and 0.87, respectively. These findings found that the result is counterintuitive because the better the human development, the lower the youth unemployment. Therefore, the economic implication of this is that the significant improvements in the quality of education, health, and income do not translate to increased youth employment. In contrast, gross domestic product and inflation relate negatively to the human development index at 0.19 and 0.33. Youth unemployment influences gross secondary school enrollment positively at 0.60. Furthermore, it supports the Phillips curve theory, indicating a negative relationship between unemployment and inflation at 0.15. From 1991 to 2022, as unemployment decreases, inflation flattens, and vice versa, at a rate of 0.40. The correlation between inflation and gross domestic product is also negative and significant at 0.40, while the link between youth unemployment and gross domestic product stands at -0.36. However, as revealed in the correlation matrix, the associations between youth unemployment, gross secondary enrollment, and the human development index have a strong brink of multicollinearity.

Table 1. Summary of descriptive statistics and pairwise correlation matrix

Variables	HDI_t	YUN_t	GES_t	INF_t	GDP_t
Unit	Index	%	%	%	%
Mean	0.4830	10.3066	35.2380	18.4196	4.0537
Maximum	0.5480	14.3520	54.8829	72.8355	15.3291
Minimum	0.4490	9.3410	23.5453	5.3880	-2.0351
Std. Dev.	0.0353	1.4280	9.3494	16.2484	3.7825
Skewness	0.4847	1.6405	0.1863	2.1591	0.4848
Kurtosis	1.7304	4.3438	1.7176	6.6228	3.7864
HDI_t	1.0000 [-----]				
YUN_t	0.8599* [9.2307]	1.0000 [-----]			
GES_t	0.8766* [9.9801]	0.6025* [4.1349]	1.0000 [-----]		
INF_t	-0.3319*** [-1.9274]	-0.1523 [-0.8445]	-0.4136** [-2.4881]	1.0000 [-----]	
GDP_t	-0.1906 [-1.0637]	-0.3656** [-2.1517]	0.1076 [0.5930]	-0.4064** [-2.4367]	1.0000 [-----]
Obs.	32 years	32 years	32 years	32 years	32 years

*, **, *** denote 1%, 5%, and 10% levels of significance, while [] depicts t-statistics.

Source: Authors’ computation.

Table 2 illustrates the relationship between youth unemployment, gross secondary enrollment, and the human development index. To address multicollinearity among these variables, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test is applied, where a centered VIF value under 10 indicates

no multicollinearity. Table 2 confirms that all centered VIF values are below 10, indicating the estimated model is free from multicollinearity issues.

Table 2. Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) multicollinearity test

Variable	Coefficient variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
YUN_t	2.57E-06	123.3178	2.251517
GES_t	5.52E-08	32.41043	2.069145
INF_t	1.28E-08	3.380844	1.453149
GDP_t	2.76E-07	3.707685	1.696453

Source: Authors' computation.

4.1.2. The Phillip-Perron standard unit root test

The PP standard unit root test assesses the stability and reaction of a series to shocks over time. It was selected for its effectiveness in correcting non-parametric heteroscedasticity and serial autocorrelation in error terms. The PP test incorporates the trend and intercept equation, which avoids the need for lag length selection and provides unique asymptotic critical values, ensuring a strong check against serial autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity.

Table 3. Phillip-Perron standard unit root test

Variables	Test equation	Level	First Difference
HDI_t	Trend and intercept	-2.1547 [-3.5628]	-3.5904 [-3.5683]
YUN_t	Trend and intercept	-0.9115 [-3.5628]	-5.6561 [-3.5683]
GES_t	Trend and intercept	-2.5233 [-3.5628]	-6.4836 [-3.5683]
INF_t	Trend and intercept	-2.8830 [-3.5628]	-8.4233 [-3.5683]
GDP_t	Trend and intercept	-2.8051 [-3.5628]	-15.8143 [-3.5683]

[] represent t-statistics. **Source:** Authors' computation.

4.2. Bounds test

Given that Table 3 indicates a non-stationary series at the first difference, implying unpredictability for a cointegration assessment arises to explore long-term trends. This study aligns with Shrestha and Bhatta (2018) and Pesaran and Shin (1995), suggesting the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach, applicable when the series exhibits order one post-unit root testing. To ascertain the series's relationship direction, a modern method developed by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001) was employed, chosen for its efficiency and suitability for small sample sizes, as noted by Haug (2002). The ARDL Bounds test, as illustrated in Eq. 4, was utilized to determine the drift order among the series.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta HDI_t = & \delta_0 + \lambda_1 HDI_{t-i} + \lambda_2 YUN_{t-i} + \lambda_3 GES_{t-i} + \lambda_4 INF_{t-i} + \lambda_5 GDP_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^a \gamma_{1i} \Delta HDI_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^b \gamma_{2j} \Delta YUN_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^b \gamma_{3j} \Delta GES_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^b \gamma_{4j} \Delta INF_{t-j} \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^b \gamma_{5j} \Delta GDP_{t-j} + \eta_t \end{aligned} \dots \text{Eq. 4}$$

Where $\lambda_1 - \lambda_5$ are the vector parameters of the long-run estimates, Δ are the operators of the first difference, a and b are the optimal lag length, $\gamma_1 - \gamma_5$ are the vector parameters of the short-run estimates, δ_0 is the constant parameter, and η_t is the white noise error term. Thus, the null hypothesis of the ARDL Bounds test, which states that there is no level relationship between the series, is expressed in Eq. 5 as,

$$H_0: \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \lambda_4 = \lambda_5 = 0 \dots \text{Eq. 5}$$

Table 4 revealed that the series are related and drift in the same direction, which also means that if there exists a shock in the short run, the series still converge and move in the same direction with time, implying that there is a long-run convergence among the series over the estimated period of time (that is, between 1991 and 2022) in Nigeria since the F-statistic is above the 5% critical value of the upper bound.

Table 4. ARDL Bounds Test

Significance	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Selected Model	F-Statistic	K
10%	2.2	3.09	ARDL (1, 2, 1, 0, 2)	17.21288	4
5%	2.56	3.49			
1%	3.29	4.37			

Source: Authors' computation.

4.3. Estimates of the ARDL and ECM effects on the human development index

Table 4 indicates that the series are interrelated and display similar directional drift, suggesting a short-term shock requiring correction, as they are expected to converge in the long run. This involves estimating the error correction term and analyzing long-run convergence via the ARDL. The adjustment for the short-run shock aims to minimize the sum of squared residuals, and given the presence of cointegration, the error correction model is developed using the ARDL Bounds test as detailed in Eq. 6.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta HDI_t = & \delta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^a \gamma_{1i} \Delta HDI_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^b \gamma_{2j} \Delta YUN_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^b \gamma_{3j} \Delta GES_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^b \gamma_{4j} \Delta INF_{t-j} \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^b \gamma_{5j} \Delta GDP_{t-j} + \omega ECT_t + \eta_t \end{aligned} \dots \text{Eq. 6}$$

Empirical findings from the short-run Error Correction model (ECM) indicate that youth unemployment in Nigeria has a positive but insignificant impact on human development

initially, while a lagged effect significantly impairs the human development index. This suggests that youth unemployment hinders economic growth and inclusive development. Additionally, secondary school enrollment shows an insignificant positive effect on human development, contradicting expectations, indicating a potential harm to human capital. Gross domestic product similarly has a positive, insignificant effect due to high youth unemployment, while lagged youth unemployment significantly obstructs human development. The error correction term reflects a 3.6% adjustment rate towards the long-run equilibrium, suggesting it would take the government approximately 2 years and 3 months to address economic shocks and restore balance.

Table 5. Empirical estimates of the ECM short-run results

Dependent variable: ΔHDI_t

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
ΔYUN_t	0.000274	0.000970	0.283012	0.7802
ΔYUN_{t-1}	-0.002270	0.001025	-2.215048	0.0392
ΔGES_{t-1}	-0.000123	0.000107	-1.153467	0.2630
ΔGDP_t	4.11E-05	0.000121	0.339928	0.7376
ΔGDP_{t-1}	-0.000599	0.000117	-5.142053	0.0001
ECT_t	-0.036344	0.003182	-11.42171	0.0000
R-squared	0.997744	Mean dependent var.		0.003300
Adjusted R-squared	0.689031	Durbin-Watson stat.		1.980481

Source: Authors' computation.

Estimates of the long-run ARDL model, as expressed in Eq. 5 and Table 6, depict the impact of the series in the model over a long period of time compared to the corrected economic shock model in Eq. 6. The long-run model in Eq. 7 is expressed based on the automatically selected model as

$$HDI_t = \delta_0 + \lambda_1 HDI_{t-1} + \lambda_2 YUN_t + \lambda_3 YUN_{t-1} + \lambda_4 YUN_{t-2} + \lambda_5 GES_t + \lambda_6 GES_{t-1} + \lambda_7 INF_t + \lambda_8 GDP_t + \lambda_9 GDP_{t-1} + \lambda_{10} GDP_{t-2} + \eta_t \quad \dots \text{Eq. 7}$$

Empirical analysis in Nigeria indicates that youth unemployment initially has a negligible positive impact on human development, transitioning to a negative effect over time, illustrating a lack of significant influence on human development and posing risks to inclusiveness and economic growth. This result is in tandem with the study of Adenike (2021). Additionally, gross secondary school enrollment initially exerts a negative impact but becomes positively significant when lagged, suggesting delayed effects on human development. This result is buoyed by the conclusions of Anand and Sen (1994), Ogunbadejo and Kanwanye (2020), and against Onabote *et al.* (2023). Inflation shows a positive yet insignificant effect, indicating potential but not decisive growth. Musa *et al.* (2024) support the result while negating the findings of Ogbekor *et al.* (2020), which reveal that inflation rates do not contribute to the human development index in Nigeria. The gross domestic product initially does not negatively affect human development, but with a lag, it shows both harmful and later supportive significant impacts, underscoring the necessity for strategic economic policies to enhance human development. Azeez (2024) supports the findings that gross domestic product promotes the human development index.

Table 6. Empirical estimates of the ARDL long-run results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
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HDI_{t-1}	0.963656	0.062340	15.45798	0.0000
YUN_t	0.000274	0.001355	0.202475	0.8417
YUN_{t-1}	-0.001515	0.001679	-0.902662	0.3780
YUN_{t-2}	0.002270	0.001370	1.656096	0.1141
GES_t	-0.000123	0.000147	-0.837016	0.4130
GES_{t-1}	0.000383	0.000151	2.545196	0.0198
INF_t	1.02E-05	3.42E-05	0.297046	0.7697
GDP_t	4.11E-05	0.000173	0.238232	0.8143
GDP_{t-1}	-0.000147	0.000169	-0.867127	0.3967
GDP_{t-2}	0.000599	0.000156	3.842554	0.0011
Constant	-0.000667	0.020031	-0.033277	0.9738
Adjusted R-squared	0.996557	Durbin-Watson stat		1.980481
F-statistic	840.3839	F-statistic prob.		0.000000

Source: Authors' computation.

4.4. Robustness checks

Table 7 evaluates the robustness of the ARDL long-run results using the Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) method, which addresses endogeneity and serial correlation issues (Stock & Watson, 1993). This approach is particularly suited to Nigeria's macroeconomic environment, marked by short data spans and structural breaks. The DOLS test confirms that gross secondary school enrollment positively impacts the human development index, reinforcing the ARDL model's findings that improving human capital leads to substantial welfare benefits over time. Both methodologies emphasize the pivotal role of education in promoting sustainable human development in Nigeria.

Youth unemployment in Nigeria does not significantly affect human development, primarily due to short-term government initiatives. While it exists statistically, the emphasis should be on sustainable job creation for the youth. Additionally, inflation's long-term impact on welfare is minimal, and inconsistent GDP growth indicates non-inclusive economic progress, resulting in persistent inequality and weak institutions. The robustness test further points out that Nigeria's human development is shaped by policy and education, but is slow to respond to macroeconomic shifts.

Table 7. Robustness DOLS results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
YUN_t	0.017238	0.008211	2.099381	0.0576
GES_t	0.002581	0.000316	8.164790	0.0000
INF_t	-0.000175	0.000195	-0.896200	0.3878
GDP_t	-0.000968	0.001060	-0.913676	0.3789
Constant	0.230536	0.081441	2.830711	0.0152
Adjusted R-squared	0.967774	Mean dep. var.		0.483103

Source: Authors' computation.

4.5. Estimates of the Granger causality tests

As indicated by the ECM and ARDL model estimates, a long-term causality link exists among the series. A causality test reveals shock directions based on the Bounds test results. Granger (1969) theory posits that one series can predict improvements in another. Table 8 presents

pairwise Granger causality test results, rejecting the null hypothesis for youth unemployment and the human development index, the human development index and gross secondary school enrollment, the human development index and gross domestic product, and a two-way causality between inflation and the human development index in Nigeria with a lag length of two. This indicates no causal direction between inflation and the human development index, while unidirectional causality is observed between youth unemployment and the human development index, as well as between the human development index and gross secondary school enrollment and gross domestic product.

Table 8. Results of the empirical pair wise Granger causality tests

Null Hypothesis:	F-Statistic	Prob.	Obs. (lag)	Decision
$YUN_t = \sum_{i=2}^g aYUN_{t-i} + \sum_{j=2}^g bHDI_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{1t}$	0.38522	0.6843	30 (2)	Reject
$HDI_t = \sum_{i=2}^g cHDI_{t-i} + \sum_{j=2}^g dYUN_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{2t}$	3.77982	0.0368		Accept
$GES_t = \sum_{i=2}^g aGES_{t-i} + \sum_{j=2}^g bHDI_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{3t}$	6.70774	0.0047	30 (2)	Accept
$HDI_t = \sum_{i=2}^g cHDI_{t-i} + \sum_{j=2}^g dGES_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{4t}$	0.24269	0.7863		Reject
$INF_t = \sum_{i=2}^g aINF_{t-i} + \sum_{j=2}^g bHDI_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{5t}$	0.57050	0.5724	30 (2)	Reject
$HDI_t = \sum_{i=2}^g cHDI_{t-i} + \sum_{j=2}^g dINF_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{6t}$	0.09918	0.9059		Reject
$GDP_t = \sum_{i=2}^g aGDP_{t-i} + \sum_{j=2}^g bHDI_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{7t}$	9.56089	0.0008	30 (2)	Accept
$HDI_t = \sum_{i=2}^g cHDI_{t-i} + \sum_{j=2}^g dGDP_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{8t}$	0.88691	0.4245		Reject

Source: Authors' computation.

4.6. Results of the model diagnostic and stability test

Estimates from the post-diagnostic test results in Table 9 revealed that the ARDL long-run and ECM short-run results models have no econometric estimation problem, indicating that the null hypothesis of the RAMSEY Reset test, the serial correlation LM test, the heteroscedasticity, the Jarque-Bera normality test, CUSUM, and the CUSUM squares were not rejected at the 5% significance level. Thus, the economic significance of the results is that the model does not have econometric misspecification.

Table 9. Estimates of the post-diagnostic test results

Diagnostic test	F-Statistic	Prob. Value	Decision
RAMSEY Reset Test	0.017725	0.8956	The model is normally distributed.
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	2.062409	0.1578	The model does not have autocorrelation.
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroskedasticity	0.936920	0.5230	The model does not contain heteroscedasticity.
Jarque-Bera normality test	0.995478	0.607904	The series is normally distributed with a bell shape.
CUSUM and CUSUM Squares	The model is fit and stable as it's free from econometric misspecification.		

Source: Authors' computation.

Figure I. CUSUM, CUSUM of Squares Test at 5% Significance and Normality Histogram.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This study analyzed the impact of youth unemployment on Nigeria's human development index from 1991 to 2022 using an error correction model. It sourced human development index data from the 2024 UNDP database and independent variables from the 2024 WDI database. The findings indicate that youth unemployment and gross secondary enrollment positively correlate with the human development index, while gross domestic product and inflation negatively affect the human development index. Long-term effects show a significant positive contribution of youth unemployment, secondary enrollment, and gross domestic product to the human development index, but inflation has a statistically insignificant impact. This is supported by the results of the DOLS. In the short term, lagged youth unemployment negatively impacts the human development index. The study estimates a 3.6% speed of adjustment to restore long-run equilibrium, taking approximately 2 years and 3 months. Additionally, Granger causality tests indicate significant relationships between youth unemployment and the human development index, as well as between the human development index and gross secondary enrollment.

The study recommends that the Federal Government, through the Ministry of Budget and Finance, should implement fiscal policy easing, demand-side subsidy programs, and labor law enforcement. Policy on the easing of fiscal measures should incorporate a deliberate attempt by the government to be involved in creating regional employment that ventures into the manufacture of necessary goods, and also increase the recruitment process of the youths into the military bases of the nation. As a matter of necessity, the Nigerian health and education sector faces huge human capital differentials, which require huge employment through oriented and specialized education in health and health. This means that more of the youths should be encouraged to venture into special education investment in education as teachers and health practitioners. This, in the long run, would reduce the persistent increase in youth unemployment and also improve the formation of human capital in the nation. Likewise, the DOLS estimation is consistent with the long-run model recommends an ongoing transparent investment in secondary education to improve employability and social mobility. Therefore, addressing youth unemployment is crucial, requiring alignment of education with industrial policies and labor market reforms. Additionally, managing inflation and maintaining fiscal discipline are essential for sustaining economic stability. As a call for further studies, this study recommends that research should be conducted to investigate the interactive effect of the youth gender gap on the human development index in Nigeria. Despite this, further study can address the investigation of how institutions affect the interaction of the effect on the human development index in Nigeria and perhaps in sub-Saharan African economies.

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